

A Structural Equation Model on the Organizational Research Culture of College Instructors in Davao Region

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Suggested Citation

Booc, N.B.B. (2023). A Structural Equation Model on the Organizational Research Culture of College Instructors in Davao Region. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), 78-91.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).09](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).09)

Abstract:

This study aimed to establish the best-fit model of organizational research culture as influenced by attitudes, capabilities, and self-efficacy toward academic research of college instructors in Davao Region. The research design used in the study was descriptive-causal design through structural equation modeling. Using a simple random sampling method, a survey questionnaire was administered to the 380 college instructors in selected private and public schools in Region XI. Findings show high attitudes, capabilities, self-efficacy, and organizational research culture. Also, there is a significant relationship and influence in attitudes, capabilities, and self-efficacy

towards academic research of college instructors on organizational research culture. There was a direct causal effect of attitudes and capabilities in academic research of college instructors on organizational research culture. Moreover, the model illustrates the total indirect or mediated effect of Capabilities on organizational research culture. This, in turn, has the potential to influence the overall culture of the institution. The capability-mediated effect can impact the research culture by facilitating individuals' participation in research-related tasks and promoting a research-focused atmosphere. It is recommended to intensify and strengthen the existing policies about research in any academic institution.

Keywords: *research attitudes, research capabilities, research self-efficacy, organizational research culture, structural equation modelling, Davao Region, Philippines.*

Introduction

Research is one of modern education's most valuable assets and critical progress indicators. However, some teachers, particularly college instructors, struggle with conducting research. It is acknowledged that their inability to comprehend the research process harms their ability to be innovative in their teaching methods. Teachers must develop practical, research-based, and scientific strategies and instruction to manifest their excellent cheerful disposition and self-efficacy in conducting research. There is also a problem with the self-efficacy and disposition of researchers in India,

where many graduate and postgraduate students, including teachers, believe that research is unnecessary and finish their research for compliance (Saini et al., 2020).

Additionally, the impact of organizational culture is a factor in performing instructional tasks such as conducting research (Rivai et al., 2019). Time spent on research-related activities significantly impacts research productivity (Al-Jabari, 2014). In private higher education institutions, the support of the institution has a substantial impact on research outcomes. In the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) is responsible for the

development of the research functions of HEIs. However, studies have revealed difficulties that hinder instructors from carrying out research, such as a lack of financial support, insufficient research knowledge and skills, and an excessive academic load (Vasquez, 2017).

In Davao City, the culture of research has been sprouting, but 13 out of the 89 full-time faculty members only engaged in conducting institutional research. Strengthening research administration through organizational, infrastructural, and human resource development is vital to match the dynamic research environment and teaching-learning processes from the classroom-based setting to the learning environment based on real-world skills (Ali et al., 2022).

This paper investigates an expanded understanding of attitudes, capabilities, self-efficacy, and organizational research culture. It aims to confirm the variables in question through a rigorous research methodology.

Statement of the Problem

This study determined a structural model of the organizational research culture of college instructors by examining dimensions of attitude, capabilities, and self-efficacy towards academic research in the academic year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of attitude towards academic research as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. course relation;
 - 1.2. research anxiety;
 - 1.3. life relation;
 - 1.4. difficulty of research; and
 - 1.5. positive attitude?
2. What is the level of capabilities towards academic research as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. research proposal;
 - 2.2. research tool;

- 2.3. data analysis;
- 2.4. data gathering; and
- 2.5. conclusions and recommendations?
3. What is the level of self-efficacy towards academic research as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. mastery experiences;
 - 3.2. vicarious experience;
 - 3.3. social persuasion; and
 - 3.4. physiological and emotional states?
4. What is the level of organizational research culture as perceived by the respondents in terms of:
 - 4.1 research resources (human & physical);
 - 4.2 research environment;
 - 4.3 research support and incentives; and
 - 4.4 research audit and publications?
5. Is there a significant relationship between attitude towards academic research and organizational research culture?
6. Is there a significant relationship between capabilities towards academic research and organizational research culture?
7. Is there a significant relationship between self-efficacy towards academic research and organizational research culture?
8. Is there a singular significant influence of attitude towards academic research on organizational research culture?
9. Is there a singular significant influence of capabilities towards academic research on organizational research culture?
10. Is there a singular significant influence of self-efficacy towards academic research on organizational research culture?
11. Is there a combined significant influence of the attitudes, capabilities, and self-efficacy towards academic research on the organizational research culture?

12. What best-fit model explains the organizational research culture of college instructors in the Davao region?

Hypotheses

This research study had the following null hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

H₀1. There is no significant relationship between attitude towards academic research and organizational research culture.

H₀2 There is no significant relationship between capabilities towards academic research and organizational research culture.

H₀3 There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy towards academic research and organizational research culture.

H₀4 There is no singular significant influence of attitude towards academic research on organizational research culture.

H₀5 There is no singular significant influence of the capabilities towards academic research on organizational research culture.

H₀6 There is no singular significant influence of self-efficacy towards academic research on organizational research culture.

H₀7 There is no combined significant influence of the organizational research culture on the attitudes, capabilities, and self-efficacy towards academic research.

H₀8 There is no model which best explains the organizational research culture of higher education institutions in the Davao Region.

Methods

The researcher employed a quantitative research design with structural equation modeling through adapted survey questionnaires as data-gathering instruments. This study was conducted among 380 private and public college instructors in Davao Region. The mean, Pearson product correlation, regression table analysis, and structural equation modeling were used to analyze the result.

Results and Discussions

Data on teachers' perceptions of academic research, their organizational research culture, and their self-efficacy are presented in this chapter.

Table 1 shows the level of attitude towards academic research as perceived by college instructors. The mean scores of the indicators are shown, course relation (M=4.26) with a very high level; research anxiety (M=3.50), life relation (M=3.84), and positive attitude (M=3.52) with a high level; and difficulty of research (M=3.36) with a moderate level. The overall mean attitude score towards academic research is 3.70 with a descriptive level of High. This suggest that college instructors have a high attitude toward academic research, which can positively impact teaching quality and student learning outcomes. Educators prioritizing research are more likely to integrate innovative pedagogical approaches and technologies supported by evidence-based research. Additionally, actively engaging in academic research and demonstrating a strong passion for their field enables educators to effectively communicate their enthusiasm to students, increasing student engagement and motivation.

Table 1. Level of Attitude Towards Academic Research as Perceived by College Instructors

Capabilities	Mean	Descriptive Level
Research Proposal	3.90	High
Research Tool	3.89	High
Data Analysis	3.80	High
Data Gathering	3.97	High
Conclusions and Recommendations	4.01	High
Overall	3.91	High

However, some studies have indicated generally unfavorable attitudes toward research, but teacher education programs have the potential to address this issue and emphasize the importance of research in professional practice (Butt &

Shams, 2013). The value attributed to research courses may vary among individuals based on their preconceived notions about the research they intend to undertake Alun et al. (2021).

Table 2. Level of Attitude towards Academic Research as Perceived by College Instructors

Attitude	Mean	Descriptive Level
Course Relation	4.26	Very High
Research Anxiety (Research Confidence)	3.50	High
Life Relation	3.84	High
Difficulty of Research (Ease of Research)	3.36	Moderate
Positive Attitude	3.54	High
Overall	3.70	High

Shown in Table 2 is the level of attitude toward academic research as perceived by college instructors. All the indicators have a high descriptive level, research proposal (M=3.90), research tool (M=2.89), data analysis (M=3.80), data gathering (M=3.97), and conclusions and recommendations (M=4.01). The overall mean score of capabilities towards academic research as perceived by college instructors is 3.91, with a high descriptive level. This suggests that educators skilled in conducting research are more likely to produce high-quality outcomes by employing rigorous methodologies, appropriate sampling techniques, accurate data collection and analysis, and effective dissemination to diverse audiences. They contribute significantly to advancing their academic disciplines and are more likely to secure financial resources and partnerships. Their ability to consistently generate superior research output attracts investment and potential collaborators while also making valuable contributions to policy and practice within their fields. These researchers possess the capacity to recognize the impact of their findings and effectively communicate them to policymakers, practitioners, and other relevant stakeholders.

However, De la Cruz (2016) conducted a study on the Research Capability of Ilocos Sur

Polytechnic College, which involved 162 faculty members. The findings indicated that the researchers demonstrated competence in conceptual skills while exhibiting moderate competency in computational and technical skills. The assertion is also contradicted by Chow et al. (2015) research, which suggests that confident educators need to improve in executing research, specifically in classroom-based or action research.

Table 3 Level of Self-Efficacy towards Academic Research as Perceived by College Instructors

Self-Efficacy	Mean	Descriptive Level
Mastery Experiences	4.02	High
Vicarious Experiences	4.04	High
Social Persuasion	4.03	High
Physiological and Emotional States	4.01	High
Overall	4.03	High

Table shows the level of self-efficacy towards academic research as perceived by college instructors. All the indicators have a high descriptive level, mastery experiences (M=4.02), vicarious experiences (M=4.04), social persuasion (M=4.03), and physiological and emotional states (M4.01). Meanwhile, the overall mean self-efficacy score towards academic research as perceived by the college instructors is 4.03, with a high descriptive level. When college professors have a strong sense of self-efficacy in academic research, they tend to be confident in their research skills and more likely to be able to deal with problems that come up during research. Their better self-efficacy makes them more interested in research, which makes them more efficient and productive. When instructors have a higher sense of self-efficacy, they are more likely to keep going even when things get hard. This can help them do better studies. This confidence also makes them more likely to look for more study opportunities, which improves their teaching methods and helps them build a reputation as good teachers in their academic circles.

This is supported by Xavier and Meneses (2022), who have discovered that these convictions indicate individuals' level of exertion, their ability to persist in the face of challenges, their capacity to self-monitor and be self-motivated, their accomplishments, and their life decisions. The concept of self-efficacy in research aligns with similar principles. As per Mozahem et al.'s (2021) citation of Bong's (1996) work, the research needs to be more comprehensive in elucidating the precise correlation between self-efficacy beliefs and other expectancy constructs. The studies have yet to be able to differentiate between them in terms of their contributions to predicting academic performance or self-regulation practices.

Table 4 Level of Organizational Research Culture as Perceived by College Instructors

Organizational Research Culture	Mean	Descriptive Level
Research Resources (Human & Physical)	3.96	High
Research Environment	4.08	High
Research Support and Incentives	3.99	High
Research Audit and Publications.	3.95	High
Overall	4.00	High

Table 4 shows the level of organizational research culture as perceived by college instructors. All the indicators have a high descriptive level, research resources (m=3.96), research environment (m=4.08), research support and incentives (m=3.99), and research audit and publications(m=3.95). Meanwhile, the overall mean score of organizational research culture perceived by college instructors is 4.00, with a high descriptive level, which means that this is often manifested. A strong organizational research culture signifies the organization's recognition of research as vital to its activities and decision-making processes. This approach promotes informed decision-making based on thorough research and analysis. Additionally, it cultivates a motivated and dedicated workforce by providing opportunities for employees to

research and expand their knowledge within an environment that encourages curiosity and inquiry. Such an approach can increase motivation and productivity among employees incentivized to pursue meaningful and impactful research endeavors. Furthermore, a robust organizational research culture can enhance the organization's reputation and credibility.

According to Pamatpat and Subillaga's (2016) affirmation, the Commission on Higher Education has reiterated that the fundamental responsibility of universities in the nation is to produce and distribute knowledge. The responsibility and function of conducting research and scholarly investigations across various disciplines should be recognized and recognized in this context, as they play a fundamental role in advancing knowledge, fostering innovation, and addressing complex societal challenges (Canti et al., 2021). Also, the collaboration between administrators and teachers aims to bring about changes in the school and promote professional development among teachers (Munafò et al., 2020).

Table 5. Significance on Relationship between Attitude towards Academic Research and Organizational Research Culture of Teachers

Organizational Research Culture	Attitude			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	.833	.000	Reject	Significant

Note: *p < 0.01

The significant relationship between attitude and Organizational Research Culture is reflected in the table. The result exhibits that the relationship between attitude towards research and organizational research culture exists with an overall p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01, hence significant at 0.01 alpha significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis is a result of this is rejected. Moreover, looking at the overall correlation coefficient, the computed r of 0.833

shows that the relationship is high or strong, further explaining that a change in one variable means an increased change in the other. Research suggests that organizations prioritizing research and fostering a supportive culture around it are more likely to cultivate positive attitudes toward research, leading to increased engagement in research activities. Negative research cultures can have adverse effects, such as reduced motivation, discontentment, and disinterest in research-related tasks. A favorable research culture promotes a fruitful and inventive research atmosphere.

The Information-Attitude-Practices Theory emphasizes cultivating a positive attitude toward research within an organization. This theory suggests that providing access to information and resources that foster a favorable perception of research and facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange among researchers is crucial for developing a strong research culture (Andrade et al., 2020). Such a culture, characterized by support and encouragement for researchers, can yield more significant and comprehensive research outcomes. Individual contributions can drive organizational progress and expansion while advancing knowledge in the respective field or industry. Organizations prioritizing research can foster a culture of improvement and innovation, enhancing performance and overall success (Wang et al., 2020).

Table 6. Significant Relationship between Capabilities towards Academic Research and Organizational Research Culture of College Instructors

Organizational Research Culture	Capabilities			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	.903	.000	Reject	Significant

The significant relationship between capabilities and Organizational Research Culture is reflected in the table. The result exhibits that relationship

between capabilities towards research and organizational research culture exists with an overall p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01, hence significant at α 0.01 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is now rejected. Moreover, the overall correlation coefficient with the computed r of 0.903 shows that the relationship is very high or very strong, further explaining that a change in one variable means a very high change in the other. This implies that a strong correlation between an organization's research culture and college instructors' capabilities may lead to a more effective and influential research setting. Instructors with research skills and knowledge are more likely to engage in research activities and produce high-quality research output. Incorporating instructors' research can enhance the research culture and reputation of the institution. Moreover, it can offer prospects for professional growth and progress for the instructors.

Table 7. Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy towards Academic Research and Organizational Research Culture of College Instructors

Organizational Research Culture	Self – Efficacy			
	r	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
	.920	.000	Reject	Significant

According to the Reinforcement Theory, rewarded behaviors are more likely to be repeated, while behaviors that face punishment are less likely to be replicated. The potential implications of a strong correlation between college instructors' capabilities and the research culture within their organization are worth exploring (Susanto et al., 2021). The reinforcement theory emphasizes positive reinforcement's significance in promoting desired behaviors, including participation in research activities and fostering a culture of research within an organization. Implementing a research-focused culture within organizations can result in many benefits, including heightened

knowledge generation and distribution, elevated teaching standards, and an improved institutional image (Bertsekas, 2019).

The significant relationship between self-efficacy and organizational research culture is reflected in the table. The result exhibits that relationship between self-efficacy towards research and organizational research culture exists with an overall p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.01, hence significant at α 0.01 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Moreover, looking at the overall correlation coefficient with the computed r of 0.920 shows that the relationship is very high or very strong, further explaining that a change in one variable means a very high change in the other. The research suggests a strong correlation between self-efficacy and organizational research culture. The research indicates that individuals with high self-efficacy beliefs are more inclined to participate in research activities and make valuable contributions to the research culture of their organization. Research has demonstrated that individuals with high levels of

self-efficacy are more likely to exhibit motivation and persistence in pursuing their objectives. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their capacity to succeed in a particular task or activity. Research findings consistently demonstrate that individuals who possess strong self-efficacy beliefs exhibit a greater propensity to engage in research endeavors.

Research indicates that self-efficacy is linked to the reinforcement theory, suggesting that individuals with high self-efficacy beliefs are more likely to engage in behaviors that lead to positive outcomes, including success in research activities (Hendricks, 2016). Positive reinforcement, such as recognition or promotion, has increased individuals' research involvement and contribution to the organizational research culture. To foster a strong research culture, organizations should provide training, mentoring, and other forms of support to enhance individuals' self-efficacy beliefs and encourage their active participation in research (Michlewski, 2016).

Table 8. Regression Analysis on the Singular Significant Influence of Attitude Towards Academic Research on Organizational Research Culture

Attitude	Organizational Research Culture						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on H_0	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.		
Constant	0.398	0.111		3.588	0.000		
Course Relation	0.480	0.040	0.500	12.063	0.000	Reject	Significant
Research Anxiety	-0.016	0.047	-0.017	-0.339	0.735	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Life Relation	0.138	0.048	0.143	2.912	0.004	Reject	Significant
Difficulty of Research	0.092	0.048	0.099	1.927	0.055	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Positive Attitude	0.217	0.052	0.240	4.195	0.000	Reject	Significant

Note: $R = .868$; $R^2 = .753$; F -value = 228.312; p -value = .000

It is shown in Table 8 the regression analysis of organizational research culture as indicated in the predictors of attitude on academic research. The use of the model predicts the attitude of teachers towards academic research as indicated

with an F -value of 228.312 and p -value of .000. This would mean that the organizational research culture is significantly influenced by the attitude of teachers towards research. Among all the indicators, there are three that significantly

influence the organizational research culture, namely Course Relation with $B = 0.480$, $t = 12.063$ and $p\text{-val} = 0.000$, Life Relation with $B = 0.138$, $t = 2.912$, and $p\text{-val} = 0.004$, and positive attitude with $B = 0.217$, $t = 4.195$, and $p\text{-val} = 0.000$. In other words, this would mean that the null hypothesis is rejected, and therefore, the indicator mentioned influences the organizational research culture. The $r\text{-square}$ value 0.753 suggests that approximately (75.3%) variance of teachers' attitudes towards academic research can be attributed to the organizational research culture of the institution.

The research culture of a group can be greatly affected by how people feel about academic research. When employees like research, they are more likely to do research themselves, share their results, and work with other researchers. This creates a research community that is active and growing. This can lead to high-quality

research results and start a positive cycle in which a strong research culture reinforces positive attitudes toward research, motivating and happy employees and keeping the organization committed to research and innovation.

The reinforcement theory can also be applied in this situation, as positive reinforcement can reinforce a positive attitude (Baroutsis, 2016). In the research context, by recognizing and rewarding employees who do research and produce high-quality research results, companies can reinforce a good research culture and get more employees to do research. This is also refuted by Abulata et al. (2019), who claim that the respondents need more time to do research due to their educational responsibilities, which causes them to lose the motivation to carry out research.

Table 9. Regression Analysis on the Singular Significant Influence of Capabilities Towards Academic Research on Organizational Research Culture

Capabilities	Organizational Research Culture						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on H_0	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.		
Constant	0.489	0.085		5.767	0.000		
Research Proposal	0.150	0.057	0.159	2.616	0.009	Rejece	Significant
Research Tool	0.190	0.059	0.205	3.210	0.001	Reject	Significant
Data Analysis	-0.009	0.046	-0.010	-0.204	0.838	Fail to Reject	Not Significant
Data Gathering	0.216	0.062	0.229	3.453	0.001	Rejece	Significant
Conclusions and Recommendations	0.339	0.057	0.363	6.001	0.000	Rejece	Significant

Note: $R = .910$; $R^2 = .828$; $F\text{-value} = 361.162$; $p\text{-value} = .000$

Shown in Table 9 is the regression analysis of organizational research culture as indicated in the predictors of capabilities on academic research. The use of the model predicts the attitude of teachers towards academic research, as shown with $F = 361.162$ and $p = .000$. This would mean that the capabilities of teachers towards research significantly influence the

organizational research culture. Among all the indicators, there are three that significantly influence the organizational research culture, namely Research Proposal with $B = 0.150$, $t = 2.616$, and $p\text{-val} = 0.009$, Research Tool with $B = 0.190$, $t = 3.210$, and $p\text{-val} = 0.001$, Data Gathering with $B = 0.216$, $t = 3.453$, and $p\text{-val} = 0.001$, and Conclusions and Recommendations

with $B = 0.339$, $t = 6.001$, and $p\text{-val} = 0.000$. In other words, this would mean that the null hypotheses are rejected, and therefore, the indicator mentioned influences the organizational research culture. The r-square value 0.828 suggests that approximately (82.8%) variance of teachers' capabilities towards academic research can be attributed to the organizational research culture of the institution.

The academic research capabilities of college professors have a significant influence on the research culture of an institution. When instructors possess the necessary skills and knowledge to engage in research, they are more likely to contribute to the growth of the research culture. Collaborative research facilitates the exchange of knowledge and ideas, fostering innovation and the development of new methodologies. Implementing this approach can lead to more impactful and innovative research outcomes, enhancing the organization's reputation in the academic community.

Additionally, research suggests that having proficient and active researchers among educators can increase the likelihood of securing funding and resources to support research endeavors, further enriching the research environment and yielding superior outcomes.

Self-determination theory says people are driven when they feel like they can do things independently (Chiu, 2022). When a person has a lot of skills, they are more likely to feel confident in their research skills, making them more likely to want to do research. Also, when people have control over their research projects, they are more likely to feel like they own and are invested in the research process. It is also pointed out by Lysova et al. (2019) that organizations that foster a sense of relatedness among employees can help build a positive research culture. College instructors who feel connected with their colleagues are more likely to share knowledge and collaborate on research projects.

Table 10. Regression Analysis on the Combined Significant Influence of Attitude, Capabilities, and Self-Efficacy Towards Academic Research on Organizational Research Culture

Model	Organizational Research Culture						
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Decision on H_0	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.		
Constant	0.061	0.075		0.807	0.420		
Attitude	0.157	0.037	0.148	4.286	0.000	Reject	Significant
Capabilities	0.292	0.044	0.298	6.580	0.000	Reject	Significant
Self-Efficacy	0.549	0.038	0.538	14.258	0.000	Reject	Significant

Note: $R = .922$; $R^2 = .887$; $F\text{-value} = 990.74$; $p\text{-value} = .000$

The use of the model predicts the combined predictor's attitude, capabilities, and self-efficacy of teachers toward academic research as indicated with $F=990.7$ and $p = .000$. This would mean that the combined predictors significantly influence the organizational research culture. The standard coefficient of self-efficacy has the highest Beta of 0.549, which implies that capabilities have the highest degree of influence on organizational research culture. It is followed

by capabilities with a beta of 0.292 and attitude with a beta of 0.157. It could be stated that there is a combined significant influence of the teachers' attitude, capabilities, and self-efficacy toward academic research on the organizational research culture of teachers. Moreover, all the predictors have a significant influence on organizational research culture, attitude with $t = 4.286$ and $p=.000$, capabilities with $t = 6.580$ and $p=0.008$, and self-efficacy with $t=14.258$ and

$p=.000$. This would mean that the null hypotheses are rejected, and therefore the predictors mentioned influence the organizational research culture. The result implies that as teachers encounter high attitudes, capabilities, and self-efficacy toward research, it tends to affect the school's organizational research culture because of the effects of those contributions, as mentioned in the indicators. The r-square value .887 suggests that approximately (88.7%) variance of the mentioned predictors towards academic research can be attributed to the organizational research culture of the institution.

The combination of capabilities, attitude, and self-efficacy plays a crucial role in shaping an organization's research culture. Strong research capabilities, positive attitudes toward research, and high self-efficacy levels contribute to increased participation in research activities, fostering a robust research culture. Moreover, individuals' motivation and job satisfaction are influenced by their research abilities, attitudes, and self-efficacy, with higher levels of competence and positive outlooks leading to greater motivation, job satisfaction, and improved productivity and performance.

Regarding motivational theory, the effect of capabilities, attitude, and self-efficacy on study can be linked to the self-determination theory, which stresses the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in motivating people (Gopalan et al., 2017). Relatedness is how people feel connected to and supported by their coworkers and the company. When people have strong skills, positive attitudes, and a high sense of self-efficacy in studying, they are more likely to feel autonomy, competence, and relatedness. This can motivate and make them happy at work (Ballesteros-Rodriguez et al., 2022).

Table 11. Best fit model on Organizational Research Culture of College Teachers

Index	Criterion	Best Fit Derived Values
CMIN/DF	< 5.00	1.261
P-VALUE	> 0.05	0.106
NFI	> 0.95	0.992
TLI	> 0.95	0.997
CFI	> 0.95	0.998
GFI	> 0.95	0.977
RMSEA	< 0.05	0.026
P-CLOSE	> 0.05	0.968

Figure 1. Best Fit Model Showing the Direct Causal Link of Attitude and Self-Efficacy and Indirect Causal Link of Capabilities Towards Organizational Research Culture and Interrelationship between Attitude, Capabilities, and Self-Efficacy

Legend:

CR - Course Relation	ME - Mastery Experiences	RA - Research Anxiety
VE - Vicarious Experiences	LR - Life Relation	SP - Social Persuasion
PA - Positive Attitudes	RR - Research Resources	RP - Research Proposal
RE - Research Environment	RT - Research Tool	RSI - Research Support & Incentives
DA - Data Analysis	RAP - Research Audit & Publications	
DG - Data Gathering	CAR – Conclusion & Recommendation	
DF - Difficulty of Research	PES - Physiological & Emotional States	

Illustrated in Table 11 are the derived values of the goodness-of-fit model indices. Also, the indices Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom (CMIN-DF), Probability Value (P-VALUE), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Root Mean Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) and Probability Close (P-CLOSE) are shown with the corresponding standard criterion used in determining best-fit model. Showed in the table are the indices CMIN/DF, P-VALUE, NFI, TLI, CFI, GFI, RMSEA, and P-CLOSE with values 1.261, 0.106, 0.992, 0.997, 0.998, 0.977, 0.026 and 0.968 respectively are all within the standard criterion.

Figure 6 shows the best-fit model for the organizational research culture of teachers. Regression weights were estimated and measured to measure the effects between measured and latent variables. The model indicates the direct attitude and self-efficacy towards research in organizational research culture (ORGRESEARCHCULTURE) with an estimated degree of influence of beta 0.67 and beta 0.41, respectively, with an error of 0.03. The result means that when attitude increases by one unit, ORGRESEARCHCULTURE increases by 0.67 plus 0.03 or minus 0.03. Similarly, when self-efficacy increases by one unit, ORGRESEARCHCULTURE increases by 0.41 plus 0.03 or minus 0.03. With a p-value of 0.000, less than 0.05, the estimated effect is significant at the alpha 0.05 significance level.

Moreover, the model illustrates the total indirect or mediated effect of capabilities on

organizational research culture, with a beta of 0.74 for self-efficacy and 0.70 for attitude degree of influence. Furthermore, the model illustrates that the interrelationship between attitude and capabilities, attitude and self-efficacy, and capabilities and self-efficacy with covariance estimates of beta 0.70, beta 0.74, and beta 0.62, respectively, is significant to alpha 0.05, a level of significance as evidenced by a p-value of 0.000.

The findings of multiple studies support the notion that attitudes, self-efficacy, and motivation have significant impacts on research culture within educational institutions. Herzberg's motivational theory (1950) suggests that the perceived importance of research influences the attitudes and abilities of college professors, ultimately shaping the institution's research culture (Corpuz, 2015). Samosa (2021) also found a strong correlation between research self-efficacy, research anxiety, research attitude, and the profiles of novice teachers and researchers, further highlighting the importance of these factors. Additionally, Alumbro et al. (2015) demonstrated that knowledge of research methodologies and experience conducting research contribute to reduced research anxiety and more positive attitudes toward research, while Abarro and Mariño (2016) discovered that teachers' research skills were influenced by their participation in seminars and training. Lastly, Horodnic and Zait's (2015) Tobit regression model revealed a connection between intrinsic motivation and research productivity, emphasizing the positive impact of research engagement on professional development.

Conclusion

The research findings emphasize the importance of attitudes, capabilities, and self-efficacy in shaping an organization's research culture. Positive attitudes toward research, coupled with high research capabilities, contribute to improved research methods, increased cooperation, and higher-quality research output. Additionally, high self-efficacy among college instructors leads to increased confidence, persistence, and motivation in research endeavors, resulting in higher-quality outcomes. Fostering a strong research culture within an organization enhances continuous learning, innovation, and decision-making, ultimately improving the organization's reputation and productivity.

The implementation of research workshops, seminars, faculty development programs, and incentives can foster a positive research attitude among college instructors while acknowledging their research accomplishments and contributions is beneficial. Establishing research policies, providing sufficient resources, fostering collaboration, and communication among faculty members and research centers can create an environment that promotes organizational research culture. Building a research culture within an institution can be facilitated by sustaining opportunities for teachers to develop their research skills, deloading their subjects to focus on research, organizing training sessions and workshops, and including research in the faculty development plan. Participating in research workshops, seminars, and training programs enhances instructors' research abilities and fosters connections with fellow researchers, while interdisciplinary research projects and engagement in institutional research endeavors contribute to a culture of collaboration. Promoting a favorable research culture attracts and retains outstanding researchers and requires collaboration, knowledge exchange, and respect. Future researchers should consider expanding the scope to include students, explore additional independent variables, and investigate other factors influencing organizational research culture.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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